

Synthesis of reduced graphene oxide decotate Cu₂S nanoparticles for cathode of quantum dot solar cell

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ABSTRACT

In this paper, the results of making a reduced graphene oxide cathode electrode with Cu₂S nanoparticles are shown so that it can be used as a counter electrode in quantum dot solar cells to replace other counter electrodes. An rGO-Cu₂S paste obtained by hydrolysis was scanned onto the surface of the fluorine-doped tin oxide (FTO) conductive substrate when bound to Cu₂S nano by a screen-printing process, then calcined at 350 °C to crystallize the film. Following calcination, the film was examined for structure using energy-dispersive X-ray (EDX) and X-ray diffraction (XRD) spectroscopy, as well as for type and particle size using scanning and transmission electron microscopy and transmission electron microscopy, respectively. Mott-schottky measurement is used to determine the semiconductor and carrier concentrations in the film, and an electrochemical device is used to assess the electrodes redox capacity in a polysulfide electrolyte solution. The operability of the rGO-Cu₂S cathode at the peak of the current density in the C-V curve was 24 mA/cm², a 30-fold increase compared to that of the Cu₂S electrode. This result shows that the efficiency, Voc, FF, Jsc are 4.92%, 0.525 V, 0.418, and 22.4 mA/cm², respectively.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Quantum dot solar cells, often referred to as quantum dot-sensitized solar cells, or QDSSCs, have been developed using a variety of QDs, including CdS, CdSe, PbS, PbSe, and InP [1], [2]. The quantum dots offer a number of advantages over dye molecules, such as the capacity to absorb multiple exciton pairs, the ability to change the bandgap energy by modifying the particle size [3], and a higher optical absorption coefficient than dye molecule particles [4], QDSSCs now have a photoelectric conversion efficiency (DSSCs) that is inferior to dye-sensitized solar cells [5]–[9].

They only partially absorb sunlight and do not fully exploit the visible spectrum because the incredible efforts [9]–[11] were carried out on single CdS or CdSe nanomaterials. In specifically, the bulk materials absorption wavelengths for CdS and CdSe are respectively 550 and 705 nm. Both materials absorption wavelengths are much shorter at the QD size than the values indicated above. After using the binding agent, the performance did not notice a significant improvement. In order to havest the efficiency, a UV-Vis spectrum of photoanodes must expand in the visible light region. Therefore, a combining CdS/CdSe nanocrystal had been carried out using numerous organizations using single QDs [12]–[15].

The counter electrode (CE), which receives electrons from the external circuit and restores the electrolyte through a redox process at the surface of the electrolyte and CE, was the subject of research in addition to that on the photoanode electrode because CE is crucial to improving the performance of QDSSCs. Therefore, a cathode must have a high porosity level in order for CE to have a large surface area of contact with the electrolyte system, a large conductivity, and a high level of electrochemical activity, which will aid in the electrolyte systems redox processes occurring more quickly, being chemically stable, and being less expensive [16].

The counter electrode (CE), which receives electrons from the external circuit and restores the electrolyte through a redox process. Therefore, a cathode must have a high porosity level in order for CE to have a large surface area of contact with the electrolyte system, a large conductivity, and a high level of electrochemical activity, which will aid in the electrolyte systems redox processes occurring more quickly, being chemically stable, and being less expensive. Researchers have searched for CEs that may achieve the aforementioned features over the years in an effort to replace the conventional CE Pt. Metal sulfide compounds such as MoS₂ [17], PbS [18], NiS [19], FeS [20], CuS [21], and Cu₂S [12] have been shown to be capable of meeting the aforementioned criteria and replacing CE Pt. Copper sulfide (CuS, Cu₂S) is employed for more investigations than the other materials in this category because it possesses a E_g of 1.1–1.4 eV, high electrochemical activity, and stability in polysulfide [22]–[24]. In order to create CEs, Cu thin films with a thickness of a few micrometers are submerged in a polysulfide. However, as immersing in a long time, the copper brass will continue to breakdown (the CuS or Cu₂S film will thicken), generating a large resistance, lowering FF and Voc, and decreasing efficiency. QDSSC yield is also decreased [22]–[24].

To develop suitable negative electrodes, several kinds of carbon have been explored recently [25]–[28]. Due to its substantial surface area, excellent conductivity, affordable manufacture, and environmental friendliness, a reduced graphene oxide is a contender to take the position of conventional negative electrodes [29]. An electrochemical properties is also significantly influenced by crystal defects or -COOH or -OH functional groups [30], [31]. Since there is no link between the layers of graphenes multilayer structure, each layer is typically incredibly thin—roughly the size of an atom. As a result, we frequently need to dope graphene with other beneficial electrochemical materials like CuS, Cu₂S, and MoS₂ to generate a graphene cathode with a suitably large porous [25], [32]–[35]. According to the studies mentioned above, the combination of rGO and Cu₂S materials generally has many benefits over other materials, making it particularly suited to be employed as a cathode for QDSSCs. In this study, we make use of rGOs advantageous transmission characteristics to assist and speed up the movement of electrons from the external circuit through counter electrodes into the electrolyte system while minimizing losses.

2. EXPERIMENTAL DETAILS

Materials: sigma of germany provided the supplies, which included graphene oxide (GO), ethylene glycol, CuCl, thiourea, polyvinylpyrrolidone (PVP), ethanol, polyethylene glycol (PEG), and substrate fluorine-doped tin oxide (FTO).

– Fabricated processes

A mixture of 20 ml of ethylene glycol mixed with 0.1 M CuCl and 0.1 M thiourea (CH₄N₂S structure), 12 mg of GO powder dissolved in 8 ml of ethanol, and 0.5 grams of PVP were produced. A complicated combination was agitated for 30 minutes at room temperature to produce a gray solution. To create a green solution, the mixture was left in an autoclave for 24 hours at 180 °C. Once at room temperature, rinse with ethanol and distilled water. The product was heated in the oven for 12 hours at 60 °C. Finally, a paste was created by swirling the aforementioned product with 10 ml of ethanol and 1.2 g of PEG at room temperature. To create the FTO/rGO-Cu₂S cathode, the paste was then screen printed onto the FTO conductive substrate and heated for 40 minutes at 350 °C.

– Characterization

To determine the surface shape and particle size, we used high-resolution scanning electron microscopy (FE-SEM) and transmission electron microscopy (TEM). FTIR spectroscopy and X-ray diffraction (XRD) are used to obtain the structure of the film. The components, elements, and percentages of the elements in the film are also determined using energy dispersive spectroscopy, which when combined with FTIR and XRD will provide us with a picture of the structure of the manufactured material. We can measure the Mott-Schottky to ascertain the semiconductor type and carrier concentration in CEs and measure the cyclic electrochemical potential curve of the cathode electrode in the solution thanks to the electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) equipment. To evaluate how well the negative electrode is working, use the polysulfide solution S₂/Sn₂-.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The results of the energy-dispersive X-ray (EDX) spectroscopy method, as shown in Figure 1, are used to determine the composition of the sample. The characteristic energy peaks for the elements C and O-2.1 keV for carbon and 1.6 keV for oxygen-appear on the corresponding EDX spectrum. The conductive glass substrates Si element as well as the measurement electrodes Au and Cu elements are among the additional elements that are present.

The percentages of elements present in the sample are listed in Table 1. The results show that the GO sample consists of two main elements: carbon and oxygen. Where the mass percent of carbon is 69.6% and that of the element oxygen is 2.4%.

Figure 1. EDX of GO powder

Table 1. The composition of elements in the GO sample

Elements	Radiant energy level	Energy peak (KeV)	Mass ratio (%)
C	K	2.1	69.6
O	K	1.6	2.4

X-ray diffraction was used to determine a structural rGO/Cu₂S film that made by the hydrothermal method at 180 °C for 24 hours. Figure 2 shows the XRD of rGO/Cu₂S powder. There were diffraction peaks of Cu₂S at diffraction angle positions of 27.2°, 35.7°, and 48.1°, corresponding to planes with miller indices (100), (102), and (110), respectively, in accordance with the standard [36], and diffraction peaks of CuS at diffraction angle positions of 33.4° and 52.7°, which correspond to planes with Miller indices (103), (108), which are consistent with JCPDS standard number 79-2321 and rGOs diffraction peaks at 22.8° and 41.4°, respectively, and correspond to planes with Miller indices of (002), (001) [34].

Figure 2. XRD of an FTO/rGO-Cu₂S counter electrode

Morphologies of the rGO and rGO-Cu₂S films on the FTO substrate, characterized by FE-SEM Figures 3(a) and (b). The rGO film showed that rGO has a spherical shape, the size is unevenly distributed, and 100 to 400 nm-size, containing many voids and porosity Figure 3(a). After rGO binds with Cu₂S nanoparticles, the porosity of the film decreases, and rGO and Cu₂S particles bind together to form a composite block.

Figure 3. FE-SEM of (a) FTO/rGO and (b) FTO/rGO-Cu₂S counter electrode

An electrochemical device is used to assess the carrier concentration and semiconductor type of manufactured materials using the Mott-Schottky method [37], [38]. EC-Lab software was used to fit and identify the semiconductor type and carrier concentration matching to the region of the manufactured film after measuring Mott-Schottky (0.196 cm²). In (1) tells us how to figure out the concentration of N carriers in the film:

$$\frac{1}{C_{SC}^2} = \frac{2}{e\epsilon\epsilon_0 N} \left(E - E_{FB} - \frac{kT}{e} \right) \quad (1)$$

Where C_{SC} is the capacitance of the film, D is the dielectric constant, and ϵ_0 is the electrical constant, E is the measured potential value of the electrode, and E_{FB} is determined when the tangent line to the graph intersects the horizontal axis where $C = 0$, k is Boltzmann constant, e is the elemental charge, and T is the ambient temperature.

From the fit results obtained in Figure 4, the ambient temperature is 25 °C, the area of the fabrication electrode is 0.196 cm², the E_{FB} is -1.752 V, the frequency is 10.015 kHz, and the carrier concentration of $0.466 \cdot 10^{24} \text{ cm}^{-3}$ is obtained corresponds to an n-type semiconductor. The large values of N facilitate the electrochemical processes at the surface of the cathode electrode with the polysulfide electrolyte system.

Figure 4. Fitted mott-schottky graph

According to the results of the structural study discussed above, Cu₂S material formed on the FTO film and was connected to the rGO materials lattice. We used an electrochemical cyclic potential scan to get the electrodes current and corresponding potential in order to analyze the electrochemical activity of the cathode electrode and the oxidation-reduction process using S²⁻/Sn²⁻ electrolyte [39]. The Figure 5 shows C-V curves of Pt, rGO-Cu₂S and rGO counter electrodes. Both electrodes operate in the solution of the polysulfide electrolyte system shown in Figures 3(a) and (b). In the C-V spectrum, the positive peak is the oxidation of S²⁻ ions to Sn²⁻, and the negative peak corresponds to the reduction of Sn²⁻ ions to S²⁻ [40], [41]. The size of the C-V peak serves as a measure of the electrodes quality; the larger the peak, the better the electrodes ability to transfer excited charges to S²⁻/Sn²⁻ electrolyte and lessen electron loss processes at the electrical surface extreme [42], [43]. The oxidation peak of the rGO-Cu₂S electrode was found to be approximately 6 mA, which is approximately 30 times that of the Pt electrode and 12 times that of rGO electrodes. The oxidation peak of the Pt electrode was approximately 0.2 mA. This finding demonstrates that the rGO-Cu₂S electrode has superior electrochemical characteristics to the Pt electrode. In the previous study by tung group and colleagues, they successfully fabricated a Cu₂S cathode electrode with a photoelectric conversion efficiency of 3.77%, many times higher than other cathode electrodes such as Pt or PbS [44].

Figure 5. C-V curve of Pt, rGO-Cu₂S and rGO counter electrodes

In this study, the QDSSCs were created using an electrode that contained a significant amount of GO. Surlyn, the polysulfide electrolyte system employed for cell operation, bonds the photoanode and cathode electrodes of QDSSCs together. We test the batteries conversion efficiency using a voltage and current density curve as shown in Figure 6. A 100 mW/cm² solar spectrum simulation light is flashed, it indicators J_{sc}, V_{oc}, FF, and efficiency of 4.92%, V_{oc} of 0.525 V, FF of 0.418, and J_{sc} of 22.4 mA/cm², among other data. It has a better efficiency than both the Pt counter electrode (2.05%, 0.47 V, 0.328, and 13.3 mA/cm²) and the rGO (3.98%, 0.515 V, 0.4, and 19.3 mA/cm²).

Figure 6. J-V curve measurement of QDSSCs with Pt and FTO/rGO-Cu₂S CEs

Figure 7 is the electrochemical resistance spectrum of QDSSCs with the FTO/rGO-Cu₂S CEs. The purpose of measuring EIS is to obtain a dynamic resistance when it operates under the influence of light. From Figure 7, we can see the resistance values Rct1 (resistance across the surface of CEs/electrolyte and diffusion of electrons in the electrolyte) and Rct2 (resistance across the surface of TiO₂/QDs and diffusion resistance inside the electrolyte and the TiO₂ semiconductor film). Here, by studying the influence of the FTO/rGO-Cu₂S counter electrode component, we focus on Rct1. As a result, after fitting the experimental impedance spectrum, we determined the value of Rct1 to be 10.9 Ω. It is smaller than that of Pt (46.7 Ω) and rGO (21.8 Ω) counter electrode. This value also is very small if compared with the results of Phuong *et al.* [44].

Figure 7. EIS of QDSSCs with an FTO/rGO-Cu₂S counter electrode

4. CONCLUSION

The rGO-Cu₂S cathodes have successfully synthesized using the hydrothermal method and screen-printing technique on a FTO conductive substrate; the active area is 0.196 cm². The morphology of the film was determined by TEM and FE-SEM with a very porous rGO surface; the diameter of the layers is about 2-3 μm, the average-sized Cu₂S nanoparticles of around 20 nm are linked on the rGO lattice. The structure of the electrode was determined by X-ray diffraction, EDX, and FTIR spectroscopy. Besides, we use the electrochemical system to determine the n-type rGO-Cu₂S electrode from mott-schottky, with carrier concentration of 0.466.1024 cm⁻³. The operability of the rGO-Cu₂S cathode at the peak of the current density in the C-V curve was 6 mA, a 30-fold increase compared to that of the Pt electrode. This result shows the outstanding capability of the electrode corresponding to efficiency, Voc, FF and Jsc of 4.92 %, 0.525 V, 0.418, and 22.4 mA/cm².

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